

The illumination - inclined circle as light source

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We view the following, see figure. The circular disk is the light source.

I = luminous intensity of the circular disk

w = surface luminous intensity density $w = \frac{I}{(2)\pi R^2}$

(2) if both sides are radiating.

r = distance midpoint of the ball - A

p = point with the searched illumination

The distance between p and A is r_1 .

$$x_2 \in [-R, +R] \quad x_1 \in [-\sqrt{R^2 - x_2^2}, +\sqrt{R^2 - x_2^2}]$$

r is vertical to x_2 and x_1 .

distance vector:
$$\vec{l} = \begin{pmatrix} r \\ x_1 \\ r_1 + x_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

For the distance l we conclude:

$$l^2 = (r_1 + x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + r^2 \quad (1)$$

The angle of inclination α of the circular disk p is:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{r_1}{r} \quad (2)$$

First the whole room is a vacuum. With formula (1) follows for the illumination:

$$\vec{E} = \int_{-R}^{+R} \int_{-\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}}^{+\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}} \frac{w}{[(r_1 + x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + r^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \left[\begin{pmatrix} r \\ 0 \\ -r_1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} \right] dx_1 dx_2 \quad (3)$$

The Gram determinant of both integrals are 1, see Forster [1] §3 and §14. In the second component is a point symmetry that means $f(-x_1) = -f(x_1)$ if $|x_1| \leq \sqrt{R^2 - x_2^2}$

$$\Rightarrow \int_{-a}^a f(x_1) dx_1 = 0$$

Reducing to an 1-dimensional vector-valued integral:

It is valid, see Bronstein [2] chapter 1.1.3.3 p.47 Nr.206:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}}^{+\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}} \frac{dx_1}{[(r_1 + x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + r^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &= \left[\frac{x_1}{(r^2 + (r_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \sqrt{(r_1 + x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + r^2}} \right]_{-\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}}^{+\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}} \\ &= \frac{2 \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - x_2^2}}{(r^2 + (r_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \sqrt{(r_1 + x_2)^2 + R^2 - x_2^2 + r^2}} \end{aligned}$$

Thus follows: $r > 0$

$$\vec{E} = 2w \cdot \int_{-R}^R \frac{\sqrt{R^2 - x_2^2}}{(r^2 + (r_1 + x_2)^2) \cdot \sqrt{(r_1 + x_2)^2 + R^2 - x_2^2 + r^2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r \\ 0 \\ -r_1 - x_2 \end{pmatrix} dx_2 \quad (4)$$

if

$$\vec{E} = \begin{pmatrix} E_x \\ E_y \\ E_z \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\Rightarrow |\vec{E}| = \sqrt{E_x^2 + E_z^2}$$

Now the medium is in the whole room. The absorption coefficient m and the density of the medium are constant. With (1) and (3) the illumination can be written:

$$\vec{E} = w \cdot \int_{-R}^{+R} \int_{-\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}}^{+\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}} \frac{e^{-m\sqrt{(r_1+x_2)^2+x_1^2+r^2}}}{[(r_1+x_2)^2+x_1^2+r^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r \\ -x_1 \\ -r_1-x_2 \end{pmatrix} dx_1 dx_2 \quad (5)$$

$$r > 0$$

In the second component is a point symmetry to x_1 , again. Because of this the integral in the second component over x_1 is zero. The following representation is possible, too.

$$\vec{E} = 2w \cdot \int_{-R}^{+R} \int_0^{+\sqrt{R^2-x_2^2}} \frac{e^{-m\sqrt{(r_1+x_2)^2+x_1^2+r^2}}}{[(r_1+x_2)^2+x_1^2+r^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r \\ 0 \\ -r_1-x_2 \end{pmatrix} dx_1 dx_2 \quad (6)$$

$$|\vec{E}| = \sqrt{E_x^2 + E_z^2} \quad r > 0$$

An approximation: for $r \gg R$

Then it is valid $l \approx \frac{r}{\cos \alpha}$ with $\tan \alpha = \frac{r_1}{r}$

Thus it follows with (6):

$$\vec{E} \approx \frac{w}{l^3} \cdot \pi R^2 e^{-ml} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r \\ 0 \\ -r_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\text{with } \sqrt{r^2 + r_1^2} = \frac{r}{\cos \alpha}$$

$$\Rightarrow |\vec{E}| \approx \frac{w}{l^3} \cdot \pi R^2 \cdot \frac{r}{\cos \alpha} \cdot e^{-ml}$$

$$\Rightarrow E_x \approx |\vec{E}| \cdot \cos \alpha$$

Now we view an example with $r_1 = R=1$ metre and luminous intensity 1 candela. We construct the following table. The illumination is presented in lux.

r [metre]	E_x	E_z	$ \vec{E} $
1	0.3573	-0.5260	0.6359
2	0.1654	-0.1180	0.2032
3	0.0897	-0.0426	0.0993
4	0.0550	-0.0196	0.0584
5	0.0368	-0.0105	0.0382
6	0.0262	-0.0062	0.0269
7	0.0195	-0.0040	0.0199
8	0.0151	-0.0027	0.0153
9	0.0120	-0.0019	0.0122
10	0.0098	-0.0014	0.0099

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition 1983 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] I.N. Bronstein, K.A. Semendjajew "Taschenbuch der Mathematik" Teubner Verlagsgesellschaft Leipsic 1985 22.edition
- [3] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001